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**Socialization and Curriculum Integration:
Emergent premises in student experiences of a first-year electrical engineering
course**

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INTRODUCTION

The integration of project based learning (PBL) into engineering curriculums has received growing interest in the engineering education research literature [1]. One particular area of interest is the first year in engineering programs [2], as it establishes the cognitive, affective, and conative foundation for students and is also closely linked to student retention and academic success [3]. At the same time, many engineering programs remain focused around theory heavy courses that provide little coupling to actual engineering practices in the first year. Balancing engineering science and engineering practices is challenging, and students often find it difficult to establish connections between different concepts, practices, and areas of engineering [4]. Furthermore, first year engineering students at today's universities often are enrolled in large anonymous courses on e.g. math, mechanics, and electronics with hundreds of other students across different engineering disciplines. Within this environment, it is difficult for the students to identify themselves as engineers in making, and be part of a disciplinary socialization process right from their first semester [5].

The context for this study is a re-designed electrical engineering program that aims at providing students with opportunities to learn engineering practices right from the start, while at the same time maintaining some of the traditional large, theory heavy, courses. Here, we explore how first year students perceive their learning environment and their transition to university. Using a national student survey as an entry point, we briefly compare the program to other electrical engineering programs in Norway before exploring the *how* and *why* of students' experiences in detail through in-depth interviews. A thematic qualitative analysis approach leads to the identification of two emergent themes that are central for the students: socialization and curriculum integration.

1 RESEARCH CONTEXT AND DESIGN

The context for this study is the five-year *Electronic System Design and Innovation* (ELSYS) integrated master study program at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU). The program curriculum was re-designed in 2014 by introducing the *Electronic Engineering Ladder* [6], an integrated sequence of four courses during the first four semesters. The aim of this ladder is to strike a balance between integrating PBL and engineering practice, with traditional engineering science course, and transform an existing program through targeted modifications, improvements, and adjustments, without the need to change the entire curriculum.

In the first semester of the ELSYS program, an introductory project-based course (ELSYS GK) was added to the curriculum, where the students get the opportunity to work on an engineering project. The second and third semester were changed by adding an engineering science course on circuit design and analysis, and signal processing, respectively. Finally, the curriculum was adjusted to include a final course in the fourth semester, where students continued to work with the project from the first semester. Here, we focus on the ELSYS GK in the first semester.

The central aim with introducing a project activity right from the first semester is to illustrate how engineers work and give students the opportunity to work in teams. Students are divided into groups of 6-8 by the teachers and there are around 15 groups each year. The general project theme is similar for all groups and defined through a collaboration with an external partner, typically a company, organization, or public institution with an authentic engineering problem. Within this general theme, the

students define and work the details of the project themselves and solve the problem within their groups.

The ELSYS GK course is organized as a full day (8-16 o'clock) over a period of 13 weeks. The day is structured around a general skeleton of different activities as shown in Figure 1. Each day starts with an introduction session called *Cross-Talk* where problems related to the current project situation are discussed and relevant theory from other parallel courses is brought in. Following the plenary session, the groups work individually, before the class has another plenary session around lunch. In this session, called *Today's Guest*, students meet an invited guest from industry who talks about their work and how electrical engineering is important for their company. After lunch, the group work continues, until a final plenary session at the end of the day, where selected groups present problems they have encountered during the day. In addition, focus sessions are held throughout the day, where one or two students from each group with similar challenges or project tasks can share experiences and learn from each other.

Fig. 1. A typical ELSYS GK day

In order to get a general understanding of the effects that the redesign of the ELSYS program has on students' experiences, we used data from an independent national student survey called Studiebarometeret administered by the Norwegian National Agency for Quality in Education (NOKUT) [7]. The survey asks students about their perception of quality in study programs at Norwegian universities and covers a wide range of topics including questions on the learning environment, professional relevance, and student involvement, amongst others. All questions are aimed at study program level, not course or institution level. The Studiebarometeret allows the comparison of the ELSYS program to other electrical engineering programs in Norway on a general level.

Using this quantitative evaluation as a starting point, we used a qualitative case study approach [8] to explore students' experiences in the first semester of the ELSYS program further. Six students volunteered and gave their informed consent to be part of the semi-structured in-depth interviews at the end of the ELSYS GK course. The students were selected to cover different levels of pre-knowledge in electronics, as well as being part of different project groups. The interviews lasted 20-45 minutes each and covered topics about students' pre-knowledge, their perception of the learning environment, and experiences coupled to their first semester curriculum. All interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed.

For the analysis, the interviews were pooled together and a thematic analysis approach [9] was used to identify, analyse and describe patterns and themes within the data. The material was read and re-read to explore what factors in the course the students described as central for their experiences. Through this iterative process, we identified different themes that emerged from the interviews. These themes were further explored by considering relevant literature and using it as an additional perspective to develop and deepen the thematic analysis. In this study, we will focus on two themes from the analysis: socialization and curriculum integration, other themes included: pre-knowledge, group work, peer-learning, and drop-out.

2 RESULTS

The ELSYS program differs from more traditional electrical engineering programs in Norway, as briefly described above. Overall the teaching approaches used in the program seem to be well received by the students. Table 1 shows a comparison of the ELSYS program with an average of other electrical engineering programs in Norway for 2015 to 2017 for four selected areas. Regarding the learning environment, the ELSYS program scores slightly higher with respect to the academic environment among students, and considerably higher on student satisfaction with the environment between students and academic staff. Furthermore, students in the ELSYS program feel slightly more that the program contributes to their motivation and say to a larger degree that their program has a good collaboration with industry.

Table 1. Comparison of ELSYS with other electrical engineering programs in Norway

NOKUT Studiebarometer [7] (1=dissatisfied/disagree; 5=satisfied/agree)	ELSYS – 5-year program at NTNU			Average of all 5-year study programs in Electronics		
	2017	2016	2015	2017	2016	2015
The academic environment among the students in the study program	4.5	4.5	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.2
The environment between the students and the academic staff in the study program	4.5	4.5	4.4	3.7	3.8	3.8
The study program contributes to your motivation for studying	4.1	4.1	4.2	3.8	3.9	3.8
The study program has good collaborations with industry	4.5	4.5	-	4.0	4.0	-

Building upon this general program evaluation, we will, in the following, focus on two themes that emerged from the qualitative analysis of the interviews: socialization and curriculum integration.

2.1 Socialization

The first theme that emerged from the interviews with the students is how the ELSYS GK course contributes to the socialization process. One important aspect that the students highlight in the socialization process is to get to know each other and feeling that they belong to the study program. They emphasize that ELSYS builds a community, where you learn each other names, get to know each other, and have teachers to relate to:

We build a very nice community in ELSYS. You learn many names, you get to know your classmates... we have a number of teachers that we meet continuously and can relate to. (Student 2)

The students experience building this type of community as the main point of the ELSYS GK course. They believe that the disciplinary learning is not at the center of the course, but that the overall goal is to have a good start at the university and get some basic ideas about group work and different working approaches:

I do not think the main point in the course is to learn so much about electronics, just to use it a bit, try it a bit, play with it. But the point is to learn a little more about group work and different working approaches and to have a very nice start in the ELSYS program ... (Student 2)

The students value this approach and the focus on building a community within ELSYS, as they feel that it helps them beyond the ELSYS GK course. By emphasizing to get to know each other and establishing a community, the students feel that they belong to something:

For me ELSYS made it much easier to get to know people. You start to recognize faces and then when you see someone later at the university you feel - It feels friendly and familiar. You feel that you are part of a community even though we are so many students. (Student 5)

This is not necessarily always the case at a large university with over 40.000 students like NTNU, especially as not all students feel comfortable or want to participate in social activities organized outside the disciplinary context of their study program. Some students pointed out that the community they found within ELSYS was enough for them:

It has been very good to get this community in the ELSYS program. I'm not very active in student association and do not enjoy social happenings very much, so I have not gotten to know a lot of other students, but the ELSYS community is enough for me. (Student 2)

While the project work and general design of the ELSYS GK course play an important role in the socialization process and community building, the students explicitly also highlight a kick-off trip at the beginning of the first semester. This trip plays a significant role, as it changes the learning environment and enables students to interact with each other and the teachers differently. The students value the possibility to talk to the teachers in a safe and relaxed environment and pointed out that this made their start at the university feel easier and less dangerous:

In the beginning, we had a trip to Munkholmen and all the professors, all the lecturers and engineers from the program joined...We sat in groups on the grass and talked together. This made it a little bit less dangerous to start at university. Also when we sat to eat, there was a professor at each table so we could talk a little. (Student 2)

The socialization process is further strengthened, as the students start to see people within the community as role models. The students point out the importance of teachers connecting concepts to authentic engineering tasks and how the multifaceted interactions with the teachers help them to identify themselves with the community:

Because [the teachers] have engineering degrees and they know what engineering actually is. They always draw parallels and make comments to what it is in the engineering world. I think this helps very much. And to feel that there is a community and something to identify yourself with. That we are going to be engineers and that [the teachers] are with us. (Student 1)

While many students do not reflect upon that their teachers are academics and not necessarily practicing engineers, some students do point out the important role that guest lectures from industry play in the socialization process. They highly value the possibility to listen to and interact with practicing engineers and learn more about how engineering work looks outside of academia:

Today's guest, I think it's been what I've been looking forward to most on Wednesdays because you can see how things are at different workplaces. [At the university] you can see professors and so on. But many of us want to go to work outside academia and here we can see what professional engineers are doing. (Student 5)

Overall, the students emphasize how the first semester in the ELSYS program contributes to their socialization process into a community and that this is something that they feel is important and valuable for them.

2.2 Curriculum Integration

The second theme that emerged from the interviews as important for the students is how the ELSYS GK course contributes to integrate different aspects of the curriculum during the first semester of the ELSYS study program. One central activity in the ELSYS GK course are Cross-Talk sessions. The students feel that this is really helps

them to see how different ideas, theories, and concepts can be used and how they link to practical implications:

The teachers are very good at the Cross-Talk sessions. They help you to see that “OK you have had that in the circuit theory and this in math. Then we can use these two things to do this.” Even if there is nothing we can do immediately, it shows at least what we have learned will be needed later... It becomes more meaningful. So I think the ELSYS GK course is very good to connect the entire program together as a whole. Because everyone has math and a couple of programs have circuit theory. But in ELSYS [the teachers] show exactly what you can use it for. I think that is very good. (Student 2)

In this way, the ELSYS GK course helps to situate theory and connect it to practice by showing concrete examples that the students more easily can relate to. As the students point out, this also helps them to differentiate their own study program from other programs and contributes to the community building presented before.

By connecting theory and practice in the course and integrating aspects of the entire study program, the students also experience that the course helps them to gain a better understanding of how the different courses contribute to the ELSYS study program:

At the beginning of each Wednesday [the teachers] tend to go through what we are doing in the other courses and show how it is related to the ELSYS GK course. So, it helps me to gain an insight into why we need all the other courses and see that it is useful to what we will learn in the future. (Student 3)

The Cross-Talk sessions help the students to see more clearly the relevance of what they are learning, how it can be used in different settings, and where they might need it in the future:

I really appreciated the Cross-Talk sessions. Seeing that what you do in other subjects is useful and relevant for something - that everything is related. I think that was good. (Student 4)

The students also point out how seeing the relevance and usefulness of the different ideas, concepts, and theories help them with their motivation. On a more general level, the ELSYS GK course connects many different elements together and the students feel that this helps them in their motivation towards becoming engineers:

What I might feel is that this course really helps me to be motivated to become an engineer... You see that the theory you learn is very useful in practice. And the course is in a way a link between all the other subjects. There is a circuit technology course, a programming course, and then you have the ELSYS GK course that just ties everything together. And that's awesome. (Student 1)

In addition, some students mentioned how the positive experiences and the satisfaction from working with the project helps them with their motivation not only for the ELSYS GK course, but has cross-motivational effects for their other courses:

I think it has been fun working on the project and really the whole course I think was awesome. And it has helped a lot with my motivation to work in this course and the other courses actually. (Student 3)

Overall, the students experiencing that the ELSYS GK course strongly couples together the entire ELSYS curriculum and greatly helps them to see the relevance and usefulness of different concepts and theories. For the students, it is critical that the teachers help them to see the connection between different parts and support them in their personal development of a more holistic view on the field, which the students describe as important for their motivation.

3 DISCUSSION

Curriculum integration was highlighted in the interviews as an important part of the ELSYS GK and as having a substantial effect on students' motivation. One of the core ideas with PBL is linking theory and practice by situating concepts and theories into practical applications [1], [4]. The ELSYS GK implements this idea through the projects, but at the same time adds an additional layer through Cross-Talk sessions, which the students valued highly. One important practical consideration for Cross-Talk is that teachers have access to the learning management system (LMS) pages of the other courses. In this way, it is possible for the teachers in the ELSYS GK to follow the progress of the students and readily adapt the Cross-Talk session to be relevant and connected to the other courses.

By making the connection between theory from other courses and students' own work explicit, the teachers *cognitively model* and make their thinking visible for students [10] on how to link theory and practice. This method helps the students in the short-term to see the relevance of the other courses that they have and contributes to their overall motivation. In addition, we argue that it also has long-term benefits, as the student learn the importance and approaches how to connect theory, concepts, and practice from different areas. Furthermore, it is through this integrated approach that the students perceive the ELSYS GK as holding the entire program curriculum together.

The second theme that emerged from the interviews with the students was the students' socialization process into a community. The students value being part of a disciplinary community and the close contact that they have amongst each other, as well as with the teachers. By considering the survey data, this appears to be something that separates the ELSYS program from many other electrical engineering programs in Norway.

The ability to build meaningful relations and belong to a community are widely recognized as important factors for human motivation and central for the learning environment [11]. However, much less is known about how first-year curriculum design decisions can support processes that lead to a sense of belonging for students [12]. The interviews in this study enable us to see glimpses of how different activities like PBL, Cross-Talk, Today's Guests, and study trips in a single course can contribute to the overall socialization process. The students relate to the teachers and see them as role models. By building these student-teacher relations, the students feel that they belong not only to a community of students, but a disciplinary community coupled to their study program. Today's Guests further contribute to this process and add a professional engineering dimension to the community.

The re-designed ELSYS program described here does not take PBL integration as far as other programs [2], but it combines PBL with approaches like Today's Guest and Cross-Talk session, as well as kick-off to provide students with a meaningful and developing environment when they start university. One advantage of this approach of targeted modifications, improvements, and adjustments is that they are easier to implement than larger curriculum changes. We argue that the approach described here provides a template to significantly improve first year engineering programs with relative simple and manageable changes, while retaining most of the existing courses.

4 CONCLUSION

Overall, the ELSYS program strikes a balance between keeping old structures and courses in place and at the same time integrate new approaches and ideas that change first year students experiences. The empirical data shows that disciplinary socialization and curriculum integration are two main areas that the ELSYS GK has a strong impact on. The course binds together the program through the integration of theories and concepts from the entire program, helps the students to build a disciplinary community, and provides them with opportunities to build engineering identities. Based on the ideas presented here, and supported by the empirical findings, we provide a case example of how targeted modifications can have program wide effects, which we hope can serve as a starting point for other educators.

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